

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Vesta Science Approach (VSA) (vir_da001)

Sergio Fonte

ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da001 session. These operations were executed as part of the VSA phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Vesta, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da001 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

sergio.fonte@inaf.it, Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica, Roma, Italy

Contents

References	1
1 Check list of the sequence vir_vsa_OpNav_002.r10.sasf	2
1.1 List of operations	3
1.2 Memories usage	3
2 Integrated sequence: da001b.00.rsoe	3
3 Appendix	4
3.1 The sequence: vir_vsa_OpNav_002.r10.sasf	4

References

- [1] M. de Sanctis et al., "The VIR Spectrometer," *ISSR*, vol. 163, no. 1–4, pp. 329–369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_vsa_OpNav_002.r10.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vsa_OpNav_002.r10.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
□	✓	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
□	✓	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vsa_OpNav_002.r10.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VSA_PowerOn_002	358268520	358268941	421
VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_002	358269120	358281737	12617
VIR_VSA_OpenCover_002	358282800	358282861	61
VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002	358282981	358286493	3512
VIR_VSA_CloseCover_002	358286581	358286642	61
VIR_VSA_PowerOff_002	358287000	639316633	281029633

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Integrated sequence: da001b.00.rsoe

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da001b.00.rsoe sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 2 calibration cubes and 7 cubes for IR channel and 7 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	□	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	□	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

3. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

3.1 The sequence: vir_vsa_OpNav_002.r10.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$MARK$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_vsa_OpNav_002.r10.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2007-001T00:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2017-001T00:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2011-088T09:19:00.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = SEQ;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_vsa_OpNav_002.r10;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc1;
12 CCSD3RE00000$MARK$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT   DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR  sfonte
18 *FILE_CPLT TRUE
19 *DATE      Tue Mar 29 09:19:00 2011
20 *SEQGEN    V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2007-001T00:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF    2017-001T00:00:00.000
23 *TITLE     VIR_VestaApproach_OPNAV_002_da001
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *VSA_OPNAV_002, 2011-130T07:02:00.000
26 *EPOCHS_END
27 *Input files used:
28 *File Type Last modified      File name
29 *****
30 $$EOH
31 $$EOD
32
33 request(VIR_VSA_PowerOn_002,
34   START_TIME, VSA_OPNAV_002-04:00:00.000,
35   TITLE, "VIR power on block",
36   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
37   PROCESSOR, "GSCI",
38   KEY, "No_Key")
39
40 spawn(1,
41   SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:00\, FROM_REQUEST_START,

```

```
42  REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\  
43  RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")  
44  ),  
45  note(1,  
46  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
47  TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_PowerOn_002: Power on VML sequence is finished"\  
48  ),  
49  end;  
50  
51  request(VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_002,  
52  START_TIME, VSA_OPNAV_002-03:50:00.000,  
53  TITLE, "VIR cool down and calibration",  
54  REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
55  PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
56  KEY, "No_Key")  
57  
58  spawn(1,  
59  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
60  REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\  
61  RT_on_board_block(vcfl_vir_calibration_full)  
62  ),  
63  command(1,  
64  SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:30:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
65  NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_002: VIR goes on STAND_BY mode"\,  
66  VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
67  ),  
68  note(1,  
69  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
70  TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_002: Full Calibration VML sequence is finished"\  
71  ),  
72  note(2,  
73  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
74  TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_FullCalibration_002: Data Volume in VR4: 0.116Gb, 120 pages, 15960 packets"\  
75  ),  
76  end;  
77  
78  request(VIR_VSA_OpenCover_002,  
79  START_TIME, VSA_OPNAV_002-00:02:00.000,  
80  TITLE, "VIR cover open",  
81  REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
82  PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
83  KEY, "No_Key")  
84  
85  command(1,  
86  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
87  NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_OpenCover_002: Open the Cover"\,  
88  VIR_TC_COVER("OPENCOVER")  
89  ),  
90  note(1,  
91  SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
92  TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_OpenCover_002: The Cover is opened"\  
93  ),  
94  end;  
95  
96  request(VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002,  
97  START_TIME, VSA_OPNAV_002+00:01:01.000,  
98  TITLE, "VIR ride-along to OpNav_02",
```

```

99     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
100    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
101    KEY, "No_Key")
102
103    command(1,
104      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:00\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
105      NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Set params: SP_MODE_5_START_ALFA, SP_MODE_5_END_ALFA,
106      SP_MODE_5_STEP_ALFA to perform 26 scan mirror steps" \,
107      VIR_TC_SET_PARAMS(3,23,24,25, -58500,58500,4500)
108    ),
109    command(2,
110      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
111      NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F, detector, 28 frame, 16
112      RepTime, integration time IR=0.1 s VIS=0.5 s" \,
113      VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", 16,27,5,15,25,5,28, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 5, "VIR_TM_SCI
114    ),
115    command(3,
116      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
117      NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
118      VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
119    ),
120    command(4,
121      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:08:10\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
122      NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: VIR goes on STAND_BY mode" \,
123      VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
124    ),
125    note(1,
126      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
127      TEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Compressed Data Volume in VR 0.054 Gibit" \
128    ),
129    command(5,
130      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:01\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
131      NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F, detector, 28 frame, 16
132      RepTime, integration time IR=0.5 s VIS=1 s" \,
133      VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", 16,27,25,18,50,5,28, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 5, "VIR_TM_SC
134    ),
135    command(6,
136      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
137      NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
138      VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
139    ),
140    command(7,
141      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:08:10\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
142      NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: VIR goes on STAND_BY mode" \,
143      VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
144    ),
145    note(2,
146      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
147      TEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Compressed Data Volume in VR 0.108 Gibit" \
148    ),
149    command(8,
150      SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:01\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
151      NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F, detector, 28 frame, 16
152      RepTime, integration time IR=0.8 s VIS=1.5 s" \,
153      VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", 16,27,40,23,75,5,28, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 5, "VIR_TM_SC

```

```
150 ),
151   command(9,
152     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
153     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
154     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
155   ),
156   command(10,
157     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:08:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
158     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: VIR goes on STAND_BY mode"\,
159     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
160   ),
161   note(3,
162     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
163     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Compressed Data Volume in VR 0.162 Gibit"\
164   ),
165   command(11,
166     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
167     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F, detector, 28 frame, 16
168     RepTime, integration time IR=1.2 s VIS=2 s"\,
169     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,27,60,25,100,5,28,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM_S
170   ),
171   command(12,
172     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
173     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
174     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
175   ),
176   command(13,
177     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:08:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
178     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: VIR goes on STAND_BY mode"\,
179     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
180   ),
181   note(4,
182     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
183     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Compressed Data Volume in VR 0.216 Gibit"\
184   ),
185   command(14,
186     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
187     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F, detector, 28 frame, 16
188     RepTime, integration time IR=1.5 s VIS=3 s"\,
189     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,27,75,43,150,5,28,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM_S
190   ),
191   command(15,
192     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
193     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
194     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
195   ),
196   command(16,
197     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:08:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
198     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: VIR goes on STAND_BY mode"\,
199     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
200   ),
201   note(5,
202     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
203     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Compressed Data Volume in VR 0.271 Gibit"\
204   ),
205   command(17,
```

```

204     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
205     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F, detector, 28 frame, 16
206     RepTime, integration time IR=3 s VIS=5 s"\,
207     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,27,150,55,250,5,28,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
208     ),
209     command(18,
210     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
211     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
212     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
213     ),
214     command(19,
215     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:08:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
216     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: VIR goes on STAND_BY mode"\,
217     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
218     ),
219     note(6,
220     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
221     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Compressed Data Volume in VR 0.325 Gibit"\
222     ),
223     command(20,
224     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
225     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F, detector, 28 frame, 16
226     RepTime, integration time IR=5 s VIS=10 s"\,
227     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",16,27,250,130,500,5,28,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",5,"VIR_TM
228     ),
229     command(21,
230     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
231     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
232     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
233     ),
234     command(22,
235     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:08:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
236     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: VIR goes on STAND_BY mode"\,
237     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
238     ),
239     note(7,
240     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
241     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CubeToVR4_002: Compressed Data Volume in VR 0.379 Gibit"\
242     ),
243     end;
244
245     request(VIR_VSA_CloseCover_002,
246     START_TIME, VSA_OPNAV_002+01:01:01.000,
247     TITLE, "VIR cover close",
248     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
249     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
250     KEY, "No_Key")
251
252     command(1,
253     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
254     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CloseCover_002: Close the Cover"\,
255     VIR_TC_COVER("CLOSECOVER")
256     ),
257     note(1,
258     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
259     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSA_CloseCover_002: The Cover is closed"\

```

```
258 ),
259 end;
260
261 request(VIR_VSA_PowerOff_002,
262   START_TIME, VSA_OPNAV_002+01:08:00.000,
263   TITLE, "VIR Power Off",
264   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
265   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
266   KEY, "No_Key")
267
268 note(1,
269   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
270   TEXT,\ "VIR_VSA_PowerOff_002: Power Off the VIR instrument"\
271 ),
272 spawn(1,
273   SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
274   REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
275   RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
276 ),
277 end;
278 $$EOF
```